

CLINICAL EVALUATION OF MEDOHAR GUGGULU AND ARJUN KWATH IN THE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DYSLIPIDEMIA WSR MEDOROGA: A CASE STUDY**¹Dr. Diksha Bahuguna, ²Vd. Vikram Gupta, ³Dr. Vibhu Powar**¹P.G. Scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa, Patanjali Ayurvedic Evum Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand.²Professor, (Department of Kayachikitsa) Patanjali Ayurvedic Evum Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand.³Assistant Professor, (Department of Kayachikitsa) Patanjali Ayurvedic Evum Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Diksha Bahuguna**

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ABSTRACT

Dyslipidemia is a common metabolic disorder characterized by abnormal levels of serum lipids and is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and diabetes.^[1] In Ayurveda, dyslipidemia can be correlated with *Medoroga*, which arises from *Meda dhatu dushti* and impaired function of *Agni*. The pathogenesis involves *Kapha* and *Meda* accumulation leading to *Srotorodha* (obstruction of channels) and systemic imbalance. While modern medicine highlights lipid abnormalities as central to disease progression.^[2] Ayurvedic literature emphasizes *nidana* (etiology), *samprapti* (pathogenesis), and *chikitsa* (management) for holistic care.^[3] Integrating both perspectives offers preventive and curative strategies that may improve clinical outcomes in managing dyslipidemia. A 29-year-old male patient was enrolled in the study to evaluate the therapeutic effect of *Medohar Guggulu* administered with *Arjun Kwath* as *Anupana* for one and half month. At the end of the intervention, the patient demonstrated marked reduction in clinical symptoms along with significant decreases in cholesterol, triglycerides, and VLDL levels.

KEYWORDS: Dyslipidemia, *Medoroga*, *Meda Dhatu Dushti*, *Agni*, *Medohar Guggulu*, *Arjun Kwath*.**INTRODUCTION**

In today's fast-paced world, easy access to low-cost food and reduced physical activity have led to lifestyle and nutritional disorders, among which dyslipidemia is a major concern. Dyslipidemia is a metabolic disorder characterized by abnormal lipid levels—high total cholesterol, LDL-C, triglycerides, or low HDL-C—contributing to atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases such as coronary artery disease, stroke, and peripheral vascular disease.^[4] Sedentary lifestyles, poor diet, obesity, and comorbidities like diabetes have increased its prevalence globally and in India.^[5]

Dyslipidemia is classified as primary (genetic) or secondary (acquired through systemic conditions or lifestyle factors).^[4] Pathophysiologically, it disrupts lipid transport and clearance, induces inflammation, and accelerates atherosclerosis. Conventional management includes lifestyle modification and pharmacological therapy, though long-term drug use may cause side effects.

Ayurveda offers a holistic approach, correlating dyslipidemia with *Medoroga* disorder of *Kapha dosha* and *Medo dhatu* caused by excessive nutrition and sedentary habits.^[6] Pathogenesis involves weakened

digestive fire (*Mandagni*), fat accumulation (*Meda*), and obstruction of fat channels (*Medovaha Srotas*), often associated with obesity (*Sthoulya*) and diabetes (*Madhumeha*).

Treatment includes *Shodhana* therapies like *Vamana*, *Virechana*, and *Lekhana Basti*, and *Shamana* therapies with herbs such as *Guggulu*, *Triphala*, and *Arjuna*.^[7] Alongside medication, Ayurvedic management emphasizes diet (*Pathya-Apathya*), exercise (*Vyayama*), daily routines (*Dinacharya*), and seasonal regimens (*Ritucharya*).^[6]

CASE REPORT

A 29 year old male patient named XYZ reported first time in Kayachikitsa department OPD of Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedic Evum Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar in April 2025 as a diagnosed case of Dyslipidemia with chief complaints of.

Table No. 1: Chief Complaints.

S.No	Chief Complaints	Duration (months)
1.	Lassitude	12
2.	Excessive Hunger	8
3.	Excessive Thirst	8

4.	Excessive Sweating	4
5.	Bad Body Odour	4

Table No. 2: General Examinations.

Examinations	Value
Pulse	82 bpm
Blood Pressure	120/76 mm/Hg
Height	170 cms
Weight	80 kg
Body Mass Index	27.7

As per the patient, he has no history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or thyroid dysfunction. He reported experiencing fatigue for the past 12 months, accompanied by excessive hunger and thirst for 8

months, and increased sweating with bad body odour for 4 months. He stated that he had previously consulted another hospital, but his symptoms persisted, prompting him to seek conservative management at our facility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As far as dyslipidemia is concerned, Ayurveda does not mention it as a separate disease entity; however, it can be correlated with disorders of *Medovaha Srotas* such as *Medoroga*, where vitiation of *Kapha dosha* and *Meda dhatu* leads to accumulation of fat and lipid imbalance. The similarity of major symptoms, including excessive body fat, lassitude, and metabolic disturbances, supports this correlation.

Table No. 3: Treatments Schedule.

S.No	Shamana Aushadhi	Matra And Sevan Kaala
1.	Medohar Guggulu (Vati) (500mg)	2 tablets x BD – After Food
2.	Arjun Kwath	100ml x BD – After Food

RESULTS

Patient’s lipid profile was improved with decline serum cholesterol, triglycerides, VLDL level after 1.5 month of medications followed by strict Pathya diet, marked

decline in symptoms were seen. Decline in the levels of cholesterol along with improvement in other lab investigations are mentioned below table.

Table No. 4: Before Treatment.

Date	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	VLDL
31/03/2025	231.99 mg/dl	418.49 mg/dl	83.70 mg/dl

Table No. 5: After Treatment.

Date	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	VLDL
15/05/2025	191.00 mg/dl	321.30 mg/dl	64.30 mg/dl

PATHOLOGY LAB & RESEARCH CENTRE
PATANJALI AYURVED HOSPITAL
(Multidimensional Service Unit of Divya Yog Mandir Trust)
Certified by NABH (Constituent Board of Quality Council of India) Certificate No. (AH-2017-0023)

Patient ID: [Redacted] Reg. Date: 15/05/2025
Name: [Redacted] Received Date: 15/05/2025 09:32:34
Sex/Age: Male, 49 Yrs Report Date: 15/05/2025 12:04:32
Ref. By: SELF Print Date: 15/05/2025 12:52:36
Specimen: EDTA, PLAIN
MR No. OPD No. [Redacted]
Test Name: Value Unit Biological Ref Interval

LIPID PROFILE

Test Name	Value	Unit	Biological Ref Interval
Total Cholesterol	191.0	mg/dl	Desirable: < 200 Borderline: 200-234 High: > 240
Serum Triglycerides	321.3	mg/dl	10.0 - 190.0
HDL Cholesterol	38.7	mg/dl	35.0 - 60.0
LDL Cholesterol	114.0	mg/dl	Desirable: < 130 Border Line: 130-159 High: > 160
VLDL Cholesterol	64.3	mg/dl	5.0 - 40.0
Serum Total / HDL Cholesterol Ratio	4.94		4.50 - 6.00
Serum LDL / HDL Cholesterol Ratio	2.95		0.00 - 3.50

TRIGLYCERIDE level > 250 mg/dL is associated with an approximately 2-6-fold greater risk of Coronary Vascular Disease. Elevation of triglyceride can be seen in Obesity, Medication, Fasting less than 12 hrs, Alcohol intake, Diabetes mellitus and Pancreatitis.

CHOLESTEROL In fractions and triglycerides are the important plasma lipids influencing cardiovascular risk factors and in the management of cardiovascular disease. Highest acceptable and optimum values of cholesterol vary with age. Values above 200 mg/dl are associated with increased risk of CVD regardless of HDL & LDL values.

HDL-CHOLESTEROL level < 35 mg/dl is associated with an increased risk of Coronary vascular disease even in the face of desirable levels of cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol.

LDL & TOTAL CHOLESTEROL levels can be adversely altered by Thyroid, Renal and Liver disease as well as hereditary factors. Based on total cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, and Total cholesterol/HDL-cholesterol ratio, patients may be divided into three risk categories.

CHOLESTEROL	LDL-CHOLESTEROL	CHOLEST. RATIO
Acceptable/Low Risk	< 130 mg/dL	< 4.5
Borderline/High Risk	130-159 mg/dL	4.5-6.0
High Risk	> 160 mg/dL	> 6.0

1. Recent studies have shown that Apolipoprotein A1 & B are the primary determinants of Coronary Artery Disease risk in an individual. Patients who have normal or abnormal Apo A1 & Apo B values. Ratio of Apo B1 to A1 is **MAJOR RISK** factor.

15.3 g/dL 13.0 - 18.0 g/dL

Technician: [Signature] Lab Technician
Pathologist: [Signature] MD Pathologist

Lipid Profile Before Treatment

Sahir Diagnostic Centre
ULTRASOUND, 3D/4D • COLOUR DOPPLER • CT SCAN • DIGITAL X-RAY • COMPUTERIZED PATHOLOGY LAB

Sample Id: [Redacted] Patient ID: [Redacted]
Patient Name: [Redacted] Received Date: 31/03/25 11:00 AM
Age/Gender: 29 Yrs/Male Reporting Date: 31/03/25 12:02 PM
Ref. By: [Redacted]

Lipid Profile

Test Name	Value	Unit	Biological Ref Interval
Cholesterol-Total	231.99	mg/dL	< 200 Desirable 200-239 Borderline High > 240 High
Triglycerides level	418.49	mg/dL	< 150 Normal 150-199 Borderline High 200-499 High > 500 Very High > 80 Major Risk for Heart
HDL Cholesterol	45.89	mg/dL	> 80 Normal < 100 Optimal 100-129 Near/Above Optimal 130-159 Borderline high 160-189 High > 190 Very High < 38 NORMAL > 38 HIGH
VLDL Cholesterol	83.70	mg/dL	3.5 - 5.0
CHOL/HDL RATIO	5.06		
LDL/HDL RATIO	2.23		2.5 - 3.5

NOTE
8-10 hours fasting sample is required

NOTE: Please intimate us for typing mistakes and send the report for correction.

Technologist: [Signature]
Dr. Shreya Goel MBBS, M.D PATHOLOGIST

Not for Medical Legal purpose. All Jurisdiction Haridwar court only

Lipid Profile After Treatment

DISCUSSION

Dyslipidemia, a metabolic disorder characterized by abnormal lipid levels, is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases.^[8] Although not described as a distinct disease in Ayurveda, its clinical features closely correlate with *Medoroga*, a disorder of *Medovaha Srotas* caused by vitiation of *Kapha dosha* and accumulation of *Meda dhatu*.^{[9][10]} *Medoroga* arises from excessive nutrition, sedentary lifestyle, and overconsumption of heavy, oily, and sweet foods, leading to *Mandagni* (weakened digestive fire) and impaired metabolism. The resulting obstruction of *Medovaha Srotas* manifests as lethargy, increased body fat, excessive appetite, and other metabolic disturbance features that mirror modern dyslipidemia.^{[10][11]}

Management of *Medoroga* involves both *Shodhana* (cleansing) therapies like *Vamana*, *Virechana*, and *Lekhana Basti*, and *Shamana* (palliative) therapies using *Medohara* and *Agnideepaka* herbs such as *Guggulu*, *Triphala*, and *Arjuna*.^[11] Alongside pharmacological interventions, lifestyle modifications including dietary regulation (*Pathya-Apathya*), regular exercise (*Vyayama*), and adherence to daily (*Dinacharya*) and seasonal (*Ritucharya*) routines are crucial.

Correlating *Medoroga* with dyslipidemia provides a holistic understanding of lipid metabolic disorders, emphasizing correction of underlying doshic imbalances and lifestyle factors rather than merely controlling laboratory values.

Here the patient was prescribed *Medohara Guggulu* and *Arjuna Kwath* as part of the Ayurvedic management plan for *Medoroga*.

Medohara Guggulu - It is a classic Ayurvedic formulation with *Suddha Guggulu* as its primary component, complemented by herbs such as *Sunthi*, *Pippali*, *Marich*, *Chitraka*, *Haritaki*, *Vibhitaki*, *Amalaki*,

Musta, and *Vaividanga*. It possesses *Katu Rasa*, *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna*, *Ushna Veerya*, and *Katu Vipaka*, which collectively enable it to pacify aggravated *Kapha* and *Vata dosha*. The formulation acts as *Deepana*, stimulating the digestive fire, and *Paachana*, enhancing metabolism, while its *Kleda-Meda shoshaka* property reduces excess moisture and fat in the body. It also functions as *Srotovishodhaka*, clearing and purifying the channels of fat metabolism, and its *Lekhana* (scraping) action aids in reducing accumulated adipose tissue. Through these multifaceted activities, *Medohara Guggulu* addresses both the symptoms and root causes of *Medoroga*, facilitating the removal of excess *Meda* and *Kapha*, correcting metabolic imbalance, improving lipid metabolism, and supporting systemic homeostasis, making it an effective therapeutic intervention for lipid disorders and related metabolic syndromes.

Terminalia Arjuna - It is a well-recognized cardiogenic that acts on atherosclerosis and, due to its *Lekhana* property, facilitates the reduction of *Meda* in the *Dhamni*, supporting cardiovascular health. *Kutki* (*Picrorhiza kurroa*), the principal ingredient of *Arogyavardhini Vati*, exhibits multiple therapeutic properties including *Lekhana*, *Medohara*, *Deepana*, and *Pachana*. It primarily enhances liver metabolism, promotes bile secretion, and supports detoxification, thereby contributing to lipid regulation and overall metabolic balance. Other herbal ingredients, such as *Triphala* and *Trikatu*, help in correcting impaired *Agni* and digestion, improve nutrient assimilation, and reduce excessive accumulation of *Meda*. Together, these herbs act synergistically to break the pathogenesis (*Samprapti*) of *Medoroga* by targeting both the vitiated *Kapha* and the accumulated fat tissue. By addressing digestive fire, lipid metabolism, and channel obstruction, this combination not only alleviates the symptoms of *Medoroga* but also supports long-term systemic balance and cardiovascular health.

Table No. 6: *Pathya Apathya*.^[12]

Pathya (Recommended)	Apathya (Avoid)
Light, easily digestible foods	Heavy, oily, and fried foods
High-fiber diet (whole grains, vegetables, fruits)	Excess sweets and sugar-rich foods
Low-fat diet	Excess ghee, butter, and other fatty foods
Regular intake of <i>Kapha-pacifying</i> foods (bitter, astringent, pungent tastes)	Overeating and irregular meals
Use of spices like <i>Trikatu</i> in moderation to stimulate digestion	Daytime sleeping (<i>divaswapna</i>)
Regular warm water intake	Alcohol and smoking
Moderate physical activity (<i>Vyayama</i>)	Sedentary lifestyle
Seasonal and daily routines (<i>Ritucharya</i> and <i>Dinacharya</i>)	Overindulgence in heavy, sweet, and oily foods

CONCLUSION

In this case, the patient's treatment also emphasized strict adherence to a *Pathya* diet, thereby avoiding *Nidana* and preventing further vitiation of *Dhatus* and *Doshas*, which contributed to significant improvement within a short period.

Medoroga, as described in classical Ayurvedic texts, closely correlates with modern dyslipidemia, manifesting as excessive body fat, metabolic disturbances, and lipid imbalances.^[12] Integrating Ayurvedic interventions such as *Medohara Guggulu* and *Arjuna Kwath*, along with lifestyle modifications, offers a holistic approach to

address the root causes of lipid disorders.^[13] These therapies act synergistically to reduce vitiated *Kapha* and accumulated *Meda*, correct digestive and metabolic dysfunctions, and restore systemic equilibrium.^[14] Clinical studies have demonstrated their efficacy in managing dyslipidemia and related metabolic conditions, with significant improvements in body weight, BMI, skin fold thickness, and serum lipid profiles.^[13] These findings underscore the potential of combining classical Ayurvedic principles with modern diagnostics to provide safe, effective, and sustainable management strategies for dyslipidemia, thereby reducing cardiovascular risk and improving overall metabolic health.^[14]

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